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Page/s	Page 1 of 13

Title

**A STANDARDS-BASED PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM BASED ON
MATHEMATICS TEACHERS' TEACHING CONFIDENCE AND FACTORS AFFECTING IT**

Authors

Dr. Analyn A. Guevara, Lead Researcher
Mr. Domingo T. Guntalilib, Jr., Primary Collaborator
Mrs. Donna Bee R. Tominez, Secondary Collaborator

Saint Mary's University
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ABSTRACT

Confidence in doing someone's work helps increase productivity, effectiveness, and efficiency. However, anxiety can interfere with and affect that confidence. For mathematics teachers, such confidence is necessary, especially since many of their students are anxious about their subject, and their confidence can help alleviate the struggles in teaching and learning for the students. Hence, this study aimed to describe the pre-service and in-service mathematics teachers' teaching confidence, the factors affecting it, and eventually design a professional development program based on the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST). This study used quantitative and qualitative methods to meet its objectives with the use of a questionnaire which was distributed to the pre-service and in-service mathematics teachers of Saint Mary's University from the Grade School Department to the College Department. Means, medians, percentages, and thematic analysis were utilized as data treatments. Results revealed that the mathematics teachers are quite confident in performing their tasks. Top three factors raised which affect their teaching confidence include students attitude and interest to learn Mathematics, preparedness and mastery of the content and not updated on the new techniques, strategies, trends and styles in teaching Mathematics. From the result, a professional development program was designed.

Keywords: *learning anxiety, pedagogical competence, self-efficacy, teaching anxiety*

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 2 of 13

INTRODUCTION

Mathematics is a requirement for completing college and finding work. As a result, students' mathematical achievement may be considered one of the most important components in their professional development. Nonetheless, due to several variables such as mathematics teaching anxiety, many students from elementary to college level have had learning difficulties and demonstrated poor arithmetic achievements (Haciomeroglu, 2014). Studies revealed that the performance of Filipino learners in mathematics is very dismal. This is also reflected in the Programs for International Student Assessment (PISA) and Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) results (Roman, 2019).

Mathematics teaching anxiety can be defined as "pre- and in-service teachers' feelings of tension and anxiety that occurs during teaching mathematical concepts, theories, and formulas or during problem-solving," according to Peker (2009 in Brown et al., 2011). This type of anxiety differs from the more commonly used term, mathematics anxiety, because it is based on an individual's anxiety about their ability to teach mathematics.

In previous studies, results show that constructivist views have a direct negative impact on anxiety about mathematics teaching self-confidence and anxiety about mathematics teaching attitude (Peker & Ulu, 2018); pre-service teachers held a low-level of mathematics teaching anxiety (Haciomeroglu, 2014); the strong link between mathematics anxiety and content knowledge-induced teaching anxiety suggests that mathematics content knowledge is a significant factor in explaining teaching anxiety (Peker & Ertekin, 2011); and mathematics anxiety and bad past experiences with mathematics did certainly result in mathematics teaching anxiety, and vice versa for pre-service teachers without mathematics anxiety (Brown et al., 2011). In addition, Brady and Bowd (2005), mathematics anxiety of pre-service teacher correlated negatively with their confidence to teach mathematics. This reveals the relationship between the two constructs. However, very few studies on mathematics teaching confidence were conducted over the years.

Bursal and Paznokas (2010) showed that pre-service teachers with low levels of mathematics anxiety are more confident in their ability to teach elementary mathematics and science than their classmates with greater levels of mathematics anxiety. There were negative correlations between preservice teachers' mathematics anxiety and their confidence in teaching primary mathematics. In teaching mathematics and statistics, Umugiraneza et al. (2016) found that teachers' confidence in teaching aspects that required links between mathematics and statistics and other learning areas was lower. Teachers also acknowledged a lack of confidence in using social media to engage in critical debate concerning mathematical and statistical statements. In addition, the study by Norton (2017) showed that pre-service teachers tended to exaggerate their ability to complete mathematical tasks appropriate for the grade level they were anticipated to teach and that their confidence and beliefs in teaching mathematics are correlated.

From the studies above, since mathematics teaching confidence is associated with factors that have been affecting success in mathematics learning, measuring this construct

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 3 of 13

properly is needed. According to McCullough (2016), teachers who are confident in their ability to teach mathematics have students who are confident in their ability to use mathematics to achieve success. This becomes self-perpetuating since students' confidence is reinforced by their mastery of mathematics, which drives perseverance and boosts confidence. Despite its importance, very few studies focused on mathematics teaching confidence. This can be associated with the lack of a well-developed scale for measuring mathematics teaching confidence. In 2011, the Confidence in Teaching Mathematics (CTM) scale was created by the TIMSS. This tool was intended for eighth grade with relatively acceptable reliability indices across countries and criterion-related validity in terms of the mathematics achievement of the learners. Hence, this study.

Through this study, several benefits await the mathematics teachers themselves, who are primary beneficiaries. They will be made aware of their confidence and will ask them to reflect on how they teach and the factors affecting their confidence. Consequently, they will benefit from a professional development program. The study will also be beneficial to the administrators who will lead their mathematics teachers in increasing their confidence and can use the same concept for the others teachers of different departments. It will also be beneficial for the students that when their mathematics teachers are confident, they will learn and feel better in their mathematics classes.

METHODOLOGY

The study employed quantitative and qualitative methods to gather data and address the objectives. A descriptive research design was used in describing the pre-service and in-service mathematics teachers' teaching confidence and the factors that affect their confidence. These descriptions determined the design of the standards-based professional development program aimed at improving their teaching confidence.

The study was conducted at Saint Mary's University, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, across all levels, i.e., grade school, junior high school and science high school, senior high school, and college department, specifically the School of Teacher Education and Humanities (STEH) where the Mathematics Department and the pre-service mathematics teachers are included.

All mathematics teachers of Saint Mary's University, from the Grade School Department to the College Department, were targeted as the respondents of this study, however, a number of them declined to participate. Also, all pre-service mathematics teachers, from the first to the fourth year of the BSEd-Mathematics program, were included.

The study used a questionnaire to gather data. Part I of the questionnaire collected data on the personal and professional profiles of the mathematics teachers. Part II was the MaTeCoS (Mathematics Teaching Confidence Scale) developed by Bautista (2022). It has a Cronbach's alpha of 0.986. Part III included an open-ended question to extract the factors that affect their teaching confidence. Their suggestions on the professional development program was also solicited.

The data gathering began with the approval of the research to be conducted in the different departments. Printed copies of the questionnaires were distributed to the

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 4 of 13

respondents, but an online questionnaire was prepared as well. For the printed ones, they were retrieved after two (2) weeks.

Means, medians and standard deviations were used to describe the level of mathematics teaching confidence, while thematic analysis was used to identify the factors that affect the respondents' teaching confidence. To develop the standards-based professional development program, their suggestions and the areas where they are at the lowest were taken into consideration.

The study was reviewed by the Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Board (SMUREB). There is no conflict of interest in the conduct of the study. The profiles of the respondents and the collected data were treated with utmost confidentiality. The accomplished questionnaires were retrieved only by the researchers and the identity of the respondents were anonymized through the assignment of pseudonyms. The data were transferred to excel in number-coded format. Except for the researchers, no one was able to identify respondents in this study. The results of the study is available for the respondents if they ask to gain access. The results of the study will be available up to 3 years under the care of the researcher.

The vulnerable populations (under 18 years old) of the study were not exploited, Respondents had the choice to continue participating or withdraw from the research at any point without consequence after fully understanding the research's purpose and questions. The informed consents were presented to pre-service and in-service mathematics teachers. This ensured that they had a complete understanding of the research purpose and how their identities and the data from them will be safeguarded.

There was no known danger associated with the respondents' participation in the study, and they received no direct benefit as well, which is completely justified. As a result of this study, they will be contributing to the growing literature on mathematics teaching confidence and eventually receive benefits once the professional development program is in place.

RESULTS and DISCUSSIONS

There were 25 participants, twenty one are females and only four are males. Eleven are pre-service teachers, seven are college graduates, three are master's degree holder and four are doctor's degree holder. Table 1 presents the profile of the respondents according to the number of years teaching mathematics.

Table 1. Profile of the Respondents according to Years in Teaching Mathematics

Years	f	Percent
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Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 5 of 13

40 years and above	2	8%
30-39	2	8%
20-29	2	8%
10-19	3	12%
1-9	5	20%
none	11	44%
Total	25	100%

The following table presents the level of teaching confidence of the pre-service and in-service mathematics teachers.

Table 2. Level of Teaching Confidence of the Pre-service and In-service Mathematics Teachers

I can...	Median	Mean	SD	Scale
select appropriate instructional resources for mathematics lessons	5.00	5.04	0.98	Quite Confident
explain mathematics lessons clearly	5.00	5.12	0.88	Quite Confident
teach mathematics lessons with mastery	5.00	4.92	0.81	Quite Confident
teach mathematics concepts effectively	5.00	4.68	0.80	Quite Confident
manage effective classroom discourse in my mathematics classes	5.00	4.76	0.97	Quite Confident
use meaningful models to assist students to understand mathematical concepts	5.00	4.84	0.90	Quite Confident
plan mathematics lessons with systematic flow	5.00	5.00	0.96	Quite Confident
make my students participative in my mathematics lessons	5.00	5.00	0.82	Quite Confident
align the level of difficulty of my activities with my students' characteristics	5.00	5.00	0.82	Quite Confident
arrange my learning environment to be conducive for my students	5.00	4.92	0.81	Quite Confident
plan for a well-prepared strategy for my mathematics lessons	5.00	4.84	0.94	Quite Confident
select appropriate mathematics assessment activities that are aligned with my lesson objectives	5.00	5.08	1.04	Quite Confident
provide appropriate and flexible scaffolding for my students to develop mathematical skills	5.00	4.84	0.75	Quite Confident
establish a fair and friendly learning environment during my mathematics lessons	5.00	5.16	0.80	Quite Confident
select the most effective teaching strategy for a particular mathematics lesson	5.00	5.00	0.91	Quite Confident
link previous mathematics lessons to the new mathematics lesson	5.00	4.96	1.10	Quite Confident
use instructional resources for mathematics lessons	5.00	4.92	1.04	Quite Confident
construct traditional and alternative assessment activities for my mathematics lessons	5.00	4.72	1.06	Quite Confident
plan mathematics lessons based on the individual differences of my students	4.00	4.40	0.87	Fairly Confident
correct common misconceptions on students on mathematics concepts	5.00	4.92	0.86	Quite Confident

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 6 of 13

teach mathematics concepts in a more comprehensible and thorough way	5.00	4.96	0.89	Quite Confident
empathize with my students' needs in my mathematics lessons	5.00	5.04	0.93	Quite Confident
assist students to acknowledge and reflect on their mistakes in my mathematics lessons	5.00	4.96	0.98	Quite Confident
be creative and have fun in my mathematics lessons	5.00	4.64	0.95	Quite Confident
facilitate communication in and with mathematics	5.00	4.88	1.01	Quite Confident
develop number sense in my students	5.00	4.96	0.89	Quite Confident
give concrete examples or experiences related to my mathematics lessons	5.00	5.04	0.84	Quite Confident
teach mathematics lessons in a fun and enjoyable way	5.00	4.92	0.76	Quite Confident
apply what I have learned in professional development programs in my mathematics lessons	5.00	5.12	0.83	Quite Confident
apply my mathematics lessons in different disciplines	5.00	5.04	0.93	Quite Confident
answer students' questions about mathematics	5.00	4.88	0.88	Quite Confident
stay focused in teaching mathematics while being observed	5.00	4.88	0.93	Quite Confident
identify better ways of teaching mathematics lessons after teaching	5.00	5.12	0.73	Quite Confident
OVERALL		4.93		Quite Confident

Results show that respondents have the highest level of teaching confidence in establishing a fair and friendly learning environment during their mathematics lessons ($m = 5.16$; $sd = 0.80$). They also agreed that they are confident in explaining mathematics lessons clearly ($m = 5.12$; $sd = 0.88$); in applying what they have learned in professional development programs in their mathematics lessons ($m = 5.12$; $sd = 0.83$); in identifying better ways of teaching mathematics lessons ($m = 5.12$; $sd = 0.73$) and in selecting appropriate mathematics assessment activities that are aligned with their lesson objectives ($m = 5.08$; $sd = 1.04$).

Among the items, the respondents are only fairly confident ($m = 4.40$; $sd = 0.87$) in planning mathematics lessons based on the individual differences of their students. Teachers are aware that they have created effective lesson plan if their students are actively participating and performing well in their assessments. Implementing an effective lesson plan ensures that the teachers are on the right track (Stock, 2022). However, because of class size and time constraint, the respondents have difficulty in planning lessons that will address the different needs of their learners.

The overall level of teaching confidence of the respondents is 4.93. This result infers that the respondents are generally “quite confident” in teaching mathematics. Studies have reported that confidence in teaching mathematics is of specific importance to teachers’ practices (Umugiraneza et al, 2016). The level “quite” suggests that the respondents are moderately good but not outstanding.

Given that the teachers’ level of teaching confidence was the focus of this study, factors that affect their confidence were elicited.

Table 3. Factors That affect Mathematics Teachers’ Teaching Confidence

Factors	n
Students attitude and interest to learn Mathematics	6

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 7 of 13

Preparedness/mastery of the content	4
New Techniques and strategies in presenting lessons/Newest trends and styles in teaching Mathematics	3
Number of teaching preparations (if too many prep. , it lacks time to prepare to new subjects)	2
Environment	2
Availability of learning materials/resources.	2
Relationship with my observing teacher/ Support from colleagues	2
Too many topics to discuss; too fast in teaching that making it fun for students were not always realized	1
Too many class disruptions	1
New subject(s) to teach	1
Students' ability	1
Competency gap and continuous connection of one topic to another for each quarter and per grade level ; spiral approach OK but takes and consumes time)	1
Experiences	1
Changing world	1
Overthinking	1
Relationship with the students	1
Communication skills	1
Skills in using technology	1
Motivation	1

Top three factors raised which affect the respondents' teaching confidence include students attitude and interest to learn mathematics, preparedness and mastery of the content and not updated on the new techniques, strategies, trends and styles in teaching Mathematics.

According to research (Davadas & Lay, 2017; Goldin et al., 2016) as cited by Hwang and Son (2021), students' attitudes toward mathematics are by-product of their varied experiences with the subject . Students with a positive attitude toward the subject tend to like mathematics, while students with a negative attitude toward it tend to dislike mathematics, regard it a useless subject and feel afraid to engage in it. As a result, they tend to avoid mathematics-related activities(Cho & Hwang, 2019). Teachers who handle these students are challenged to motivate them to have a change of heart and give mathematics a chance. This indeed is a factor that affects teaching confidence.

Educational research literature agrees that teachers should know the mathematics they are teaching, and that this should be accompanied by high levels of confidence and self-efficacy (Norton,2017).This is easily said than done. Preparedness and mastery of the content is also one of the primary factors that affect teaching confidence because of several reasons. These include number of teaching preparations, too many topics to discuss, experiences and the changing world. Teachers are expected to master their subject matter even beyond the limits of the curriculum to enable them to teach effectively and explain to the learners.The mastery of their subject matter

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 8 of 13

capacitates them to help their learners to grasp and understand the appropriate knowledge, skills, attitudes and values. Without mastery of the content, the teaching-learning process fails. Research emphasized the importance of mastery of subject matter to increase teachers' confidence and teaching effectiveness (Christensen,2020).

Based on the results of this study, it is recommended that there is a need to improve the level of teaching confidence of the the pre-service and in-service mathematics teachers. The school should embark on trainings to upskill them to improve the level of their teaching confidence. There is need for the respondents to try and understand the perceptions of their students and try to adopt instructional strategies that whatever student perceived as difficult may be properly addressed to motivate and encourage students to see the need in learning mathematics and improve their performance.

Proposed Development Program

A development program entitled “**ABC in Math (Achieving and Building Confidence in Teaching Mathematics): A Standards-based Professional Development Program**” was crafted to build and/or achieve the desired level of teaching confidence of mathematics teachers.

A detailed proposal is laid down below.

A Professional Development Plan

**I. Title: ABC in Math (Achieving and Building Confidence in Teaching Mathematics):
A Standards-based Professional Development Program**

II. Objectives:

General:

The primary goal of this Achieving and Building Confidence in Teaching Mathematics (ABC in Math) Program is to deepen the pre-service and in-service mathematics teachers' teaching confidence.

Specific: The program aims to:

1. Organize activities that will intensify mathematics teachers' pedagogical content knowledge and conceptual understanding of mathematics content;
2. Provide an avenue that will deepen mathematics teachers' pedagogical content knowledge and conceptual understanding of mathematics content by exposing them to innovative and creative approaches.

III. Target Participants

The project locale is Saint Mary's University, School of Graduate Studies. The target beneficiaries are the pre-service and in-service mathematics teachers from the Grade School Department to the College Department and interested graduate students.

IV. Schedule of Implementation

This will be a **five-month** development program.

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 9 of 13

V. Work Plan

Topics	Resource Persons	Schedule of Implementation
Confidence	A	First Month
Math Content (pedagogical content knowledge and conceptual understanding of mathematics content)	Dr. Analyn A. Guevara Mr. Domingo Guntalilib Jr. Mrs. Donna Bee R. Tomines	Second Month
Technology and New Trends	B C	Third Month
Special Topics/Sharing of Best Practices	D	Fourth Month

CONCLUSION

This paper explored the level of teaching confidence of the pre-service and in-service mathematics teachers and the factors that affect their teaching confidence. The findings revealed that the respondents are quite confident in performing their tasks, Some results are similar to those reported by other research. The respondents showed higher confidence in establishing a fair and friendly learning environment during their mathematics lessons, in explaining mathematics lessons clearly, in applying what they have learned in professional development programs in their mathematics lessons, in identifying better ways of teaching mathematics lessons and in selecting appropriate mathematics assessment activities that are aligned with their lesson objectives The result for confidence level in planning mathematics lessons based on the individual differences of their students was relatively lower. The findings indicate that the teachers' confidence levels were different for different skills. Over-all, The pre-service and in-service mathematics teachers are quite confident in teaching mathematics.

Top three factors raised which affect the respondents teaching confidence include students attitude and interest to learn Mathematics, preparedness and mastery of the content and not updated on the new techniques, strategies , trends and styles in teaching Mathematics. These indicated that mathematics teachers need to be given more support to improve their level of teaching competence. From the result, a professional development program was designed and recommended.

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Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 10 of 13

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Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 11 of 13

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Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 12 of 13

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Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 13 of 13

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